

An Analytical Model to Estimate Stretch Depth and Stretch Force in Cup Drawing

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Abstract

In a typical cup drawing process, as the punch descend at a suitable speed reveals two major phases; stretching and drawing on the drawn blank. Initially the blank is stretched plastically over the whole punch face to a certain stretch depth while the blank diameter at the outer flange portion remains unchanged. Once the stretching phase is completed the drawing phase begins, in which the outer flange portion of the blank start run-in into the die hole up to the required drawing depth to form the wall of the cup. In the drawing phase the tension force arises from the resistance to drawing of the flange. At the start of the drawing process, the blank is to be stretched over the punch in order to yield the flange. As the flange start yielding, it will start run-in into the die cavity. Therefore, the blank material which in contact with the punch, unsupported zone and in contact with die mouth is to be stretched to some extent in order to transmit the forces required to start yielding in the flange. This paper describes analytical models for predicting the stretch depth and the stretch force required to draw a blank of metal into the die cavity. These models considering the effect of yield stress, coefficient of friction, die and punch geometry parameters, blank thickness variation and limiting drawing ratio. The models provide designer a valuable tool to overcome wrinkling or localized thinning of the blank in the drawing phase as well as they can be used in deep drawing simulations computer programs to determine accurate stretch phase parameters. The methodology presented here has the potential to be extended to determine a range of stretch factor for each metal to be used as a safe control limits during the forming process.

Keywords: Cup drawing; Drawing ratio; forming process; Computer model

1. Introduction

Deep drawing is one of the most important processes for sheet-metal forming. It is the base for the mass production of part pieces for many different applications, such as lighter casings or parts of automobile bodies. The drawing operation is performed by means of mated pair of forming members, the punch and the draw ring or die. Flat circular blank is centred over the mouth of the die. The punch is forced down against the flat blank by the action of the press ram. In a typical forming process, as the punch descend at a suitable speed reveals two major phases; stretching and drawing phases on the drawn blank. Initially the blank is stretched plastically over the whole punch face to a certain small stretch depth “hst”, while the blank diameter at the outer flange portion remain unchanged. The stretching phase of the blank over the punch which arise from the resistance of the outer flange region to draw (to plastic deformation)

into the die cavity, in principle depend on the blank holder force, the blank material, the friction conditions, type and method of application of lubricant, blank thickness and drawing ratio. Once the stretching phase is completed the drawing phase begins, in which the outer flange portion of the blank “the blank edge “start run –in into the die hole up to the required drawing depth added to the stretch depth to form the wall of the cup. The remaining part of the blank may take the form of small annular flange [1,2,3]. On the other hand, the blank holder is more sensitive to variation in friction conditions, die misalignment and blank thickness variation. If the restraining force is too low, too much material flows into the die causing wrinkling in the part. If, however, the restraining force is too high, not enough material flows into the die causing splitting in the part [4]. Therefore, for any final part depth and forming conditions is to define a range of “safe” control parameters that avoids part failure. More practically, the problem

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boils down to “What can be measured?” and “how can it be measured?” so that we can establish the correct operational parameters [3]. The objective of the present work is to develop an analytical model represents the stretch depth up to the instant at which the edge will start to run-in in a typical deep drawing process of a circular blanks, into a flanged cylindrical cups. The stretch depth analytical model is introduced at different drawing conditions of initial blank thickness, amount of thickness strain, die and punch profile radii and stretch angle that affect the edge run-in during the drawing process of a cylindrical cup. In addition to the above mentioned parameters the effect of die geometry is considered also as geometrical parameter that affects the dependent parameter stretch depth. Also the stretch force is taken into consideration as a stretch factor which equal to the stretch stress by the yield stress ratio of the material as a function of the drawing parameters of drawing ratio, initial blank thickness, stretch angle, thickness strain, punch radius and die profile radius.

2. Previous work

2.1 The drawing force

The punch force (or the drawing force) required to initiate plastic flow in the flange at the end of the stretch phase and the beginning of the drawing phase [1], would given by

$$F_{dr} = \pi D_p \sigma_f t_0 \left[\ln \beta_{max} + \frac{\mu \lambda (\beta_{max}^2 - 1)}{(t_0 / R_p) \beta_{max}} + \frac{t}{2r_d + t} \right] \dots (1)$$

3.2 Blank holder pressure

In deep drawing unless the sheet is held flat on the die by blank holder, the annular flange will buckle and crimp. This is a product defect referred to as wrinkling. To avoid metal folding (wrinkling) round the punch it is necessary to hold it flat between the upper surface of the die and the face of a blank holder. The amount of pressure provided by the blank holder should be just sufficient to prevent wrinkling and yet be light enough to allow the material to slip in the drawing force direction and sink into the die cavity. On the other hand, if the blank holding pressure is not sufficient at any time during the drawing operation, the flange will buckle causing flange

wrinkling. The amount of blank holder pressure required to prevent wrinkling is about (1/3) of the drawing pressure [3,5,6]. The blank holder force should be just sufficient to prevent wrinkling and experience shows that an average pressure on the flange of 1-2% of the flow stress, σ_f , of the sheet is suitable. Expressing this as fraction λ , the blank holder force can be written as [1]

$$B = \lambda \sigma_f \pi R_p^2 (\beta^2 - 1) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

2.3 Die profile radius

The die profile radius is the radius over the top edge of the hole of the die or of the die ring. As the die profile radius is increased, a 35 percent decrease in the punch load may occur. The general design rule is that the radius should fall between $2t_0$ and $10t_0$ where t_0 is the thickness of the metal. Any increase in the die radius beyond $10t_0$ does not result in a proportional decrease in the drawing force. The work expended in bending and unbending the sheet as it flows over the die profile radius increase with the ratio of the sheet thickness to radius of curvature of the die profile, causing higher drawing forces and lower LDRs (Limiting Drawing Ratio). However, if the die radius is too large, wrinkling of the sheet can occur in

the unsupported region between the die and the punch [7].

2.4 Punch Profile Radius:

The punch profile radius is the radius of the leading edge of a flat-bottomed punch. Its increase does not have a very significant effect on the drawing force. It does have some effect if the die radius is also varied [7].

2.5 Drawing ratio

Drawing ratio is defined as the ratio of blank diameter to the throat diameter of the die and the maximum ratio for which a successful draw can be made is known as the limiting deep-drawing ratio (LDR). It was found that for any given drawing conditions, the punch load increases with the blank diameter in an approximately linear manner over the whole of the useful range with a slight tendency

to drop near the limiting drawing ratio. Experimental results of thickness strain measurement show that, there is very little strain over the flat part of the punch head, except at the highest drawing ratio where the rapid development of neck at the lower end of the cup wall near its junction with the punch profile radius leading to fracture at this point, is to be noted [8]

According to Panknin and Grosch [9], when isotropic materials and tools of fixed dimensions are used the limiting drawing ratio depend mainly on the friction condition at the punch and the die. The smaller the friction at the die and the blank holder and the larger the coefficient of friction at the punch the larger are the achievable limiting drawing ratio.

Doege [2] have developed a new optical sensor principal for the contact-free recording of the material flow with high resolution. The developed sensor was used for on-line recording of the local material flow during the deep drawing process of a rectangular blank. The data obtained using this measurement procedure was employed to analyse the local deformation of radial line. The control components in order to realizing the closed loop control of the material flow were developed. The researchers have noted down that the sensor could be utilized instead of using expensive optical systems or manual methods (e.g. with measurement grid) for the deformation measurement. The material flow path was measured in eight critical position of the rectangular blank on the flange area of a die versus drawing depth. A plot of material flow versus drawing depth was shown Fig (1) in which the effect of a stretch region phase is cleared but the research has been manly restricted to the material flow path of the drawing process phase.

Fig(1) Material flow path versus Drawing depth(mm) [2]

Siegret, K. and his research team [10] at the institute for metal forming technology at the University of Stuttgart have developed a deep drawing die in which the lower binder is composed of individual segments in which the blank holder is applied using several hydraulic cylinders. The developed method and its construction allows for the distinct separation of the individual regions of the blank holder with the added possibility of being able to optimally set the blank holder force in each region. Also an inductive sensor has developed for measuring the flow-in of the edge of the blank. The sensor consists of a thin sheet metal tongue which is thinner than the blank. The sheet metal tongue is pressed against the blank edge by means of a spring and measures the blank edge position as function of punch stroke. A plot of edge run-in versus punch stroke has been shown in the research work. The plot shows that too high flow-in of material leads to wrinkles and that too low flow-in of the material leads to tears (fracture). Between these is the region which corresponds to good part (defect free). In the presented diagram the stretch phase of the drawn blank is clear and included through the desired flow curve as a basic stage of the drawing process fig. (2). In this work the methodology to use a closed-loop control to maintain the blank holder force in the working region was introduced.

Fig (2) working range for blank holder forces and edge run-in [10]

Lo,S-W and Jeng ,G-M [11] have developed a compact economy displacement sensor using an effective photo-electric fibber. The developed sensor is small enough to be embedded inside the mould in order to be used to monitor the displacement of sheet metal on the die shoulder. The investigators have proposed a simple method to evaluate the strains of the products, based on the readout of the new sensor. The work included a diagram in which it is clear how the stretch depth can be affected by varying the blank holder force fig. (3).

Fig(3)Blank displacement versus punch stroke for different blank holder pressure[11]

Ziegler,M.C.,[12] have investigated the effect of pulsating blank holder force for improving the draw ability of blank material. The research work presented a diagram showing how the stretch depth is sensitive to variation in coulomb friction coefficient fig. (4).

Fig(4)Blank displacement versus punch stroke for different friction coefficient at flange –blank contact area[12]

From the literature survey, it is evident that few attempts have been made to evaluate the stretch depth and the stretch stress in conventional deep drawing with respect to coulomb friction coefficient, limiting drawing ratio, blank material, initial plate thickness, thickness strain, and punch and die geometry.

Krishna and Swamy, [13] have analysed deep drawing process with varying punch and die geometry using finite element analysis and simulation of deep drawing process. the obtained results allow to find optimum drawing ratio in deep drawing.

Shah and others [14], have determined the most critical parameters that defects and thinning in blank using statistical and experimental methods.

3.work method

3.1 Calculation of tangential Cross Sectional Area at the punch face for any stretch angle 'θ' (between 0 and 90°) during the stretch phase of the drawing process Fig (5):

Fig(5) Calculation of the tangential cross sectional area at the punch face during the stretch face of the drawing process

$$xg = fm \text{ \& } gb = me \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

$$xg = R_p - r_p \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

$$gb = r_p \sin\theta \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

$$bj = \frac{t}{\sin\theta} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

From 4 and 5

$$Xb = xg + gb \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

$$\text{Or } Xb = [R_p + r_p(\sin\theta - 1)] \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

From 6 and 8

$$Xj = xb + bj \dots\dots\dots(9)$$

$$\text{Or } Xj = [R_p + r_p(\sin\theta - 1)] + \frac{t}{\sin\theta} \dots\dots\dots(10)$$

From 6 and 8 it follows that

$$A_{eff} = \pi(xj)^2 - \pi(xb)^2 \dots\dots\dots(11)$$

Or

$$A_{eff} = \pi \left[\frac{t^2}{\sin^2\theta} + \frac{2t}{\sin\theta} (R_p + r_p(\sin\theta - 1)) \right] \dots\dots(12)$$

3.2 Calculation of the stretch depth

The question that is usually arise in mind, how the stretch depth in deep drawing can be defined? The stretch depth in deep drawing can be defined as the depth to which it is possible to deform (to stretch) a blank material until the moment at which the flange will start with drawn (start of yielding) into the die cavity producing product free of wrinkling or fracture. In the present analysis the deformed blank thickness is assumed to be of constant thickness t at the punch, die curvatures and the unsupported zone, ie thickness variation in this region up to the end of the stretch phase is negligible.

$$Q = L - \left\{ \sin\theta \left[r_p + r_d + \frac{t}{2} + \frac{t_d}{2} \right] \right\} \dots\dots(13)$$

$$L' = \frac{L - \left\{ \sin \theta \left[r_p + r_d + \frac{t}{2} + \frac{t_d}{2} \right] \right\}}{\cos \theta} \dots\dots(14)$$

$$Q' = L' \sin \theta \dots\dots(15)$$

$$Z' = r_d + t_0 - \left[r_d + \frac{t_d}{2} \right] \cos \theta \dots\dots(16)$$

$$Z = r_p - \left[r_p + \frac{t_p}{2} \right] \cos \theta \dots\dots(17)$$

$$h_{st} = Z + Z' + Q' \dots\dots(18)$$

If it is assumed that $t_d = t_p = t$ during the stretch face it follows that

$$h_{st} = (r_p + r_d + t)(1 - \sec \theta) - \Delta t + L \tan \theta \dots\dots(19)$$

3.3 Calculation of principal strains at the punch, die profile, radii and in the unsupported zone

The strain distribution in the deformed blank, in general, high strain is associated with regions of high curvature of the punch profile, but this is influenced by friction. If the friction is high, the sheet tends to stick on the punch and deformation is concentrated near the tangent point and in the unsupported zone. This may decrease the punch depth at failure in a flat-bottomed punch. But increased it at a more pointed punch. From constancy of volume;

$$\varphi_t + \varphi_\theta + \varphi_r = 0 \dots\dots(20)$$

$$\varphi_t = \ln \frac{t}{t_0} \dots\dots(21)$$

$$\varphi = \left\{ \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \right) (\varphi_t^2 + \varphi_\theta^2 + \varphi_r^2) \right\}^{1/2} \dots\dots(22)$$

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The stretch depth can be written in plastic engineering strain form for

$$\varepsilon_t = \frac{\Delta t}{t_0} \dots\dots(23)$$

and $\Delta t = t - t_0$ as :

$$h_{st} = (r_p + r_d + t_0)(1 - \sec \theta) + L \tan \theta - t_0 \varepsilon_t \sec \theta$$

or

$$\varepsilon_t = \frac{[L \tan \theta + (r_p + r_d + t_0)(1 - \sec \theta)] - h_{st}}{t_0 \sec \theta} \dots(24)$$

or Or in term of true thickness strain ,it can be written as

$$h_{st} = (r_p + r_d + t_0)(1 - \sec \theta) + L \tan \theta + t_0(1 - e^{\varphi_t}) \sec \theta \dots(25)$$

And

$$\varphi_t = \ln \left[1 - \frac{\{ h_{st} - [L \tan \theta + (r_p + r_d + t_0)(1 - \sec \theta)] \}}{t_0 \sec \theta} \right] \dots(26)$$

And so h_{st} should be kept within certain range to avoid wrinkles or tear of blank for a given material ,and it can be written in inequality form as

$$(r_p + r_d + t_0)(1 - \sec \theta_{\min}) + L \tan \theta_{\min} - t_0 \varepsilon_t \sec \theta_{\min} \leq h_{st} \leq (r_p + r_d + t_0)(1 - \sec \theta_{\max}) + L \tan \theta_{\max} - t_0 \varepsilon_t \sec \theta_{\max} \dots\dots(27)$$

Let L_{df} to be the deformed radial length stating from die profile radius-flange junction point to the punch profile radius-punch bottom junction point.

$$L_{df} = L' + \theta(r_p + r_d + t) \dots\dots(28)$$

$$\Delta l = L_{df} - L \dots\dots(29)$$

$$\Delta l = \frac{L - \sin \theta (r_p + r_d + t)}{\cos \theta} + \theta (r_p + r_d + t) - L \dots\dots(30)$$

From fig (7) it is clear that the radial strain can be calculated as

$$\varphi_r = \ln \frac{R_0 + \Delta l}{R_0} \dots\dots\dots (31) \quad \text{Or using equation}$$

No(30) and (31) it can be calculated as

$$\varphi_r = \ln \left\{ \frac{R_0 + (r_p + r_d + t)(\theta - \tan \theta) + L(\sec \theta - 1)}{R_0} \right\} \dots\dots (32)$$

Or

$$\varphi_r = \ln \left\{ \frac{R_0 + (r_p + r_d + t_0 e^{\varphi_r})(\theta - \tan \theta) + L(\sec \theta - 1)}{R_0} \right\} \dots\dots (33)$$

From equations No. (32) and (20) the circumferential strain can be calculated as

$$\varphi_\theta = -\varphi_r - \ln \left\{ \frac{R_0 + (r_p + r_d + t_0 e^{\varphi_r})(\theta - \tan \theta) + L(\sec \theta - 1)}{R_0} \right\} \dots\dots (34)$$

Or

$$\varphi_\theta = -\ln \left\{ \frac{t}{t_0} \right\} - \ln \left\{ \frac{R_0 + (r_p + r_d + t_0 e^{\varphi_r})(\theta - \tan \theta) + L(\sec \theta - 1)}{R_0} \right\} \dots\dots (35)$$

3.4 Stretch factor

In deep drawing the tension force arises from the resistance to drawing of the flange. At the start of the drawing process, the blank is to be stretched over the punch in order to yield the flange. As the flange start yielding, it will start run into the die cavity. Therefore, the blank material which in contact with the punch, unsupported zone and in contact with die mouth is to be stretched to some extent in order to transmit the forces required to start yielding in the flange. The above discussion leads to thinking about a relation between the stretch stress and the flow strength of the flange material. If the sheet metal is to be drawn with in a safe range of forming parameters, there should be a limiting stretching factor level over which the blank can be drawn without failure. The stretch ratio level can be defined as the ratio of the cup wall stress to the flow strength of flange (onset of yielding in the flange). These two properties simply can be represented by a stretch factor.

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$$\frac{\sigma_{st}}{\sigma_{f_0}} = q_{st} \dots\dots\dots (36)$$

There by if q_{st} is small, the blank can be drawn to a limited depth before wrinkling. From the other side if the stretch stress by the flow stress ratio is too large the sheet may tear. Because of friction at the flange and die radius the wall tension must exceed that of the flange, if the flow stress in the flange reach σ_{f_0} then the stretch stress by the flow stress ratio must be approximately kept within a certain range of increasing factor as

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{st}}{\sigma_{f_0}} \right)_{\min} \leq q_{st} \leq \left(\frac{\sigma_{st}}{\sigma_{f_0}} \right)_{\max} \dots\dots (37)$$

If we assume that $\sigma_{f_0} = \sigma_y$ then the stretch factor relation can be written as:

$$\frac{\sigma_{st}}{\sigma_y} = q_{st} \dots\dots\dots (38)$$

and the punch force at the end of the stretch face can be calculated as

$$F_p = \pi \sigma_{st} \left[\frac{t^2}{\sin \theta} + 2t(R_p + r_p(\sin \theta - 1)) \right] \dots\dots (39)$$

From equilibrium condition at the end of the stretch phase we have $F_{dr} = F_p$ and by equating equation no. (1) with equation no (38) then stretch factor can be introduced by the following relation.

$$\frac{\sigma_{st}}{\sigma_{f_0}} = \frac{D_p t_0 \left[\ln \beta_{\max} + \frac{\mu \lambda (\beta_{\max}^2 - 1)}{(t_0 / R_p) \beta_{\max}} + \frac{t}{2r_d + t} \right]}{\left[\frac{t^2}{\sin \theta} + 2t[R_p + r_p(\sin \theta - 1)] \right]} \dots\dots (40) \quad \text{Or}$$

$$q_{st} = \frac{\sigma_{st}}{\sigma_y} = \frac{D_p \left[\ln \beta_{\max} + \frac{\mu \lambda (\beta_{\max}^2 - 1)}{(t_0 / R_p) \beta_{\max}} + \frac{t_0 e^{\varphi_r}}{2r_d + t_0 e^{\varphi_r}} \right]}{\left[\frac{t_0 e^{2\varphi_r}}{\sin \theta} + 2e^{\varphi_r} [R_p + r_p(\sin \theta - 1)] \right]} \dots\dots (41)$$

3. Result and Discussion

Figures 6 through 11 show the effect of varying the stretch ratio on the considered the drawing parameters of die and punch geometry and blank material of, stretch depth, die and punch profile radius, limiting drawing ratio, blank strain

Fig (6) Stretch depth h_{st} versus Stretch factor q_{st} where $R_0=100\text{mm}$, $t_0=1\text{mm}$, $r_p=10\text{mm}$, $r_d=10\text{mm}$, $\beta_{max}=2$, $\lambda=0.02$, $L=21.5\text{mm}$, $\phi_t/\theta=-0.00224523/\text{degree}$

Fig(7) True thickness strain ϕ_t , true circumferential strain ϕ_θ , true radial strain ϕ_r and true effective strain ϕ versus Stretch factor q_{st} where $R_0=100\text{mm}$, $t_0=1\text{mm}$, $r_p=10\text{mm}$, $r_d=10\text{mm}$, $L=21.5\text{mm}$, $\phi_t/\theta=-0.00224523/\text{degree}$, $\beta_{max}=2$, $\lambda=0.02$, $\mu=0.14$ Figure(6) shows the stretch depth h_{st} versus the stretch factor q_{st} . It can be seen that the stretch depth behave like a strain with the variation of the stretch factor and there is an ultimate stretch factor which should not be reached to avoid tear of the cup to be drawn.

Figure (7) shows the variation of the principal strains $\phi_t, \phi_\theta, \phi_r$ and the effective strain ϕ

versus the stretch factor. It can be seen that the thickness strain ϕ_t have the largest strain value with negative sign and after it comes the circumferential strain ϕ_θ and the radial strain ϕ_r is the smallest one while the effective or the representative strain ϕ is a little bit greater or equal to thickness strain $|\phi_t|$. Fig(8) shows that the limiting drawing ratio

Fig (8) the Limiting drawing ratio β_{max} versus Stretch factor q_{st} for different friction coefficient μ Where $R_0=100\text{mm}$, $DP=100\text{mm}$, $t_0=1\text{mm}$, $r_p=10\text{mm}$, $\theta_{max}=9^\circ$, $\beta_{max}=2$, $\lambda=0.02$, $h_{st}=3.16226\text{mm}$, $\phi_t=-0.0202$, $\phi_\theta=0.0178$, $\phi_r=0.00240$, $\phi=0.02207$.

Fig (9) Initial blank thickness t_0 in mm versus Limiting drawing ratio β_{max} , where, $q_{st}=1.09008$, $h_{st}=3.48656\text{mm}$, $\phi_t=-0.02245$, $\mu=0.14$, $\lambda=0.02$, $r_p=10\text{mm}$, $r_d=10\text{mm}$, $L=21.5\text{mm}$, $\phi_t/\theta=-0.00224523/\text{degree}$.

Fig (10) Stretch depth h_{st} in mm versus stretch factor for different combination of die and punch profiles radii where $R_0=100\text{mm}$, $t_0=1\text{mm}$, $\mu=0.14$, $L=21.5\text{mm}$, $\phi_t/\theta=-0.00224523/\text{degree}$, $\beta_{max}=2$, $\lambda=0.02$

Fig(11) Variation of r_p and /or r_d versus stretch factor where $R_0=100\text{mm}$, $t_0=1\text{mm}$, $\mu=0.14$, $L=21.5\text{mm}$, $\phi_t/\theta=-0.00224523/\text{degree}$, $\beta_{max}=2$, $\lambda=0.02$

β_{max} increases as the stretch factor increase q_{st} for a given material and also increases as the coulomb friction coefficient μ decreases for the same material (ie depending on the type of lubricant used). Figure(9) demonstrate the effect of increase in relative equivalent punch diameter (D_p/t_0) with respect to limiting drawing ratio, B_{max} for different friction conditions of $\mu=0.14$ and $\mu=0.18$. It can be seen that the limiting drawing ratio for a given sheet metal decreases as the relative punch diameter (D_p/t_0) increases, which is in a good agreement with the experimental curve presented in fig(2) of Lange [4]. Also the graph shows that the limiting drawing ratio decreases with increasing coulomb friction coefficient μ . Fig (10) shows the effect of different combinations of die and punch profile radii on stretch depth –stretch factor curve. It can be seen that when a combination of $r_p=5\text{mm}$ smaller

than $r_d=10\text{mm}$ is used result in stretch factor less than one and so increases the tendency of formation of wrinkles, whereas using of $r_p=r_d=10\text{mm}$ gives stretch factor greater than 1 which means that the blank became in a stretch state. It can be seen also that when $r_p=10\text{mm}$ greater than $r_d=5\text{mm}$ the blank is exposed to a higher stretch conditions and may be fail by tear. Fig (11) Shows the variation of r_p and /or r_d versus stretch factor. It can be seen that increasing of r_p for constant $r_d=15\text{mm}$ does not have any very significant effect on the stretch factor q_{st} and it has some effect if the die profile radius is also varied. Also this figure shows that increasing of r_d at constant $r_p=15\text{mm}$ is preferably to be kept between $2t_0$ and $10t_0$ in order to avoid unnecessary stretching of the blank.

4. Conclusions

A First time equation for estimating a new forming parameters stretching ratio q_{st} and h_{st} in cup drawing including LDR or (β_{max}), friction coefficient μ , punch radius R_p , punch profile radius r_p die profile radius r_d , initial blank thickness t_0 , deformed blank thickness t , and stretch angle θ in degrees are developed in an explicit form. The developed stretching factor equation adequately explores the correct interaction between the various parameters in the stretch phase in cup drawing while the stretch depth equation describes the exact movable geometrical interaction between the punch, die, and their associated movement parameters. An associated equation for calculating the stretch force F_{st} is also derived. Since the developed q_{st} and h_{st} equations avoid the complexities of the advanced plastic theory of nonlinear deformation. It is thereby possible to be used as a part in computer program simulations to control the stretch limits in deep drawing working floors.

Nomenclature

- D_0 = Initial blank diameter “mm “
- R_0 = Initial blank radius “mm “
- D_p = Punch diameter “mm “
- R_p = Punch radius “mm “
- R_d = Die radius “mm “
- r_p = Punch profile radius “mm “
- r_d = Die Profile radius “mm “

t_0 = Initial blank thickness "mm"
 t = Thickness of deformed (stretched) blank at the contact point with the punch profile radius at β_{max} in "mm"
 θ = Stretch angle in degree
 θ_{max} = Maximum stretch angle in degree
 $L = r_p + rd + \text{die clearance} = r_p + rd + 1.5$ "mm"
 h_{st} = Stretch depth at β_{max} in "mm"
 B = Blank holder force (N)
 σ_f = Flow stress of the sheet (N/mm²)
 σ_{st} = Stretch stress at the punch profile radius at the end of the stretch phase (N/mm²)
 F_p = punch force at the end of the stretch phase (N)
 μ = Friction coefficient at the punch, die profile radius and flange - blank contact area
 σ_y = Yield strength of blank material (N/mm²)
 ϕ_r = True radial strain
 ϕ_t = True thickness strain
 ϕ_θ = True circumferential strain
 ϕ = Effective strain
 β_{max} = Limiting drawing ratio
 $\beta = \text{Drawing ratio} = D_0 / D_p$
 ϵ_t = Engineering thickness strain
 μ = the Coulomb friction coefficient at flange-blank contact area
 λ = value $0.01 < \lambda < 0.02$
 σ_{f_0} = Flow stress through the flange at instant at which the edge will start to run-in into the die cavity (N/mm²).

A_{eff} = Tangential cross sectional area of the deformed blank at the punch face (mm²)

5. REFERENCES

1. Maricniak, Z., Duncan, J.L., "The Mechanics of Sheet Metal Forming", Eduard Arnold, First Edition, 1992. London, UK.
2. Doge E., Shmidt-Jürgensen R., Huninink S., Yun J-W, "Development of Optical sensor for The Measurement of material flow in Deep Drawing Process", Annals of The CIRP. No(1), Vol.52, January 2003, PP., 225-228. Oxford, UK.
3. Berger M., Zussman E., "On-Line Thinning Measurement in The Deep Drawing Process" ASME Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering, No(2), Vol.124, May 2002, PP.420-424, USA.
4. Slatr, R.A.C., "Engineering Plasticity Theory and Application to Metal Forming Processes", Macmillan press, 1977, New York Dublin, UK.
5. El Wakil S. D., "Processes and Design for Manufacturing" Prentice-Hall International, Inc., 1989. New Jersey, USA.
6. Pandey P.C., Singh C.K., "Production Engineering Sciences", Nem Chand Jain, Kumar Printing Service, Fifth Edition, 1984, Nai Sarak, Delhi, India.
7. Mielnik E. M., "Metal working Science and Engineering", McGraw-Hill Inc., 1991, New York, USA.
8. Johnson, W., Mamalis, "Aspects of the plasticity mechanics of some sheet metal forming processes", Hellenic Steel, 1978. Thessaloniki, Greece.
9. Lange K., "Hand Book of Metal Forming", McGraw-Hill, 1985, New York, USA.
10. Siegert K., Dannenman E., Wagner S., Galaiko A., "Closed-Loop Control System for Blank Holder Forces in Deep drawing" Annals of the Cirp vol. 44/1/1995, pp251-254, Oxford, UK.
11. Lo S-W, and Jeng, G-M, "Monitoring the displacement of blank in a Deep Drawing Process By Using a New Embedded - Type Sensor", International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, No (11), Vol, 15, 1999, pp 815-821, London, UK.
12. Ziegler, M.C., "Schwingende Niederhalterkräfte und Regelkreise beim Tiefziehen axialsymmetrischer Blechformteile" Dissertation, 1999 Universität Stuttgart. Deutschland

13.Krishna K.K., and Swamy M.K., " Prediction of Draw Ratio in Deep Drawing through Software Simulations" International Refereed Journal of Engineering and science(IRJEDS), 2014,3(12), PP.24-29. e-ISSN: 2319-183X.

14.Shan K. T., Chaudhary S., and Bhatt, " Analysis of The effect of Process parameters in Deep drawing", International Journal of Advanced Engineering and Research Development(IJAERD), 1(15), 2014, e-ISSN:2348-4470.